

CONCEPT AND CLASSIFICATION OF STATE AWARDS IN THE LEGAL INCENTIVE SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. The article examines the concept and classification of state awards within the legal incentive system, legal incentive measures for awards, legislation on awards, law enforcement practices, description of the grounds for awards, and characteristics of state awards. Based on this analysis, suggestions and recommendations are provided.

Keywords. Legal incentive, legal incentive system, award, state awards, optimization of award policy, grounds for awards, state awards in the incentive system.

Legal incentives are complex in structure. State awards are considered the most important and universal means of incentives. State awards are used to regulate all spheres of public life. The importance of this tool for society is determined by the effective influence of incentives on the consciousness and behavior of individuals.

When discussing awards as the most effective legal incentive, it is possible to highlight aspects that fundamentally distinguish them from other types of incentives (privileges, immunity, etc.): legal incentives are provided for performing socially beneficial legal actions, including conscientious fulfillment of one's obligations and outstanding service.

State awards are one of the important forms of incentives used to ensure the development of all spheres of public life, as well as to strengthen friendly relations between Uzbekistan and foreign countries. The significance and value of incentives are manifested in their positive impact on the consciousness and behavior of specific individuals.

A comprehensive study of state awards is aimed at systematizing existing knowledge about this form of incentives and drawing certain conclusions, including identifying the mechanism of influence in the formation of its active-positive personality traits; developing the main concepts of the analyzed legal phenomenon; justifying the effectiveness of determining the reasons for the absence of influence on the effectiveness of the institution of state awards; identifying the principles of interdependence of its constituent parts, the presence of their characteristic features; developing proposals and recommendations for

At the same time, the analysis of legal incentives helps to show the place and significance of state awards in the system of legal incentives. State awards are distinguished as an independent form of state legal incentives and can be classified as follows: determining the status of legal entities (changing the legal status of the subject of law, content); regulated by the norms of constitutional law (classification by subject of legal regulation); providing additional incentives (classification by benefits); paying only for high service (characterizing the degree of significance) [1. - 16 c.].

State awards are a form (measure) of high positive incentives, associated with great responsibility, fame, and respect. Its transfer will be carried out in an official, solemn manner. The nomination of a worthy candidate for the award is an art necessary in a country that needs heroes. Therefore, awards are a very serious issue and require appropriate state policy.

At the same time, the system of state awards is constantly changing and improving in accordance with the development of society.

In any policy, science, which shapes ideas in various spheres of society's life, is of great importance. In such a stimulating policy, the importance of science is incomparable, it is precisely it that should illuminate the path of this policy, create conditions for its effective implementation.

To optimize the awarding policy and ensure the full development of state activity in this area, an independent discipline and a special subject of study - the law of awards - is required [2. - p. 222].

At the beginning of the 20th century, Russian legal scholar P.A. Sorokin addressed this issue. In his opinion, while the science of crime and punishment (criminal law) had become overly extensive, the science of heroic deeds and rewards, or if necessary, the law of awards, had not even found a place among academic disciplines [3. - p. 77].

According to Professor A.V. Malko, the science of award law gradually contributes to the formation of an independent branch of legislation - legislation on awards. Currently, a sub-branch of legislation is being formed at the intersection of constitutional, administrative, and labor laws, with its general and special parts, as well as the awarding process, taking shape.

Increasing the effectiveness of the state awards system depends on a set of measures that need to be implemented within the framework of the state's incentive policy. In our view, the policy of rewarding refers to the directions of activity carried out by state authorities in the field of recognizing individuals, their collectives, and regions for their outstanding services to society and the state.

The analysis of legislation on awarding, the systematization of law enforcement practice, and the characterization of the grounds for awarding allow for the identification of the following features of state awards: First, they are established by the highest body of state power. In accordance with Article 78 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the establishment of state awards and titles constitutes the joint powers of the Legislative Chamber and the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Second, they are the highest form of official recognition for citizens and other subjects. Third, they are valid throughout the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Fourth, decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the conferment of state awards are announced in the media. Fifth, they have a specific symbolic representation in the form of orders and medals. The Law on the Establishment of Orders and Medals in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Regulation on Orders and Medals enshrine their external characteristics. Sixth, the factual basis for the presentation of state awards is the outstanding services demonstrated. Seventh, the legal basis for awarding state honors is a factual composition that encompasses a system of legal facts: the achievement of outstanding service results by the subject; submission of a nomination; coordination of the nomination by various state bodies; adoption of a legal act on conferring a specific award to the honored person (organization). Eighth, they change the legal status of the awarded person. In this respect, state awards differ from other types of incentives, such as honorary certificates, valuable gifts, or promotions in service. Ninth, they belong to a specific person.

The efforts of members of society to achieve the tasks and goals facing the state are regularly encouraged. - Б. 69-72. In Uzbekistan, "state awards and honorary titles are the

highest form of rewarding citizens for high merits in the economy, science, culture, art, protection of the Motherland and other spheres of public life" [4. - Б. 471.

The Russian scholar V.M. Duel defines the state award as follows: "A state award is an official form of higher incentive, which is used by a state body to positively evaluate the high service of a certain legal entity, has a certain external symbolic expression (orders, medals) and creates a legal consequence in the form of a lifelong change in the legal status of a subject." - 16 c.].

The prize, as the most important form of moral, state-official approval of the activity of the incentivized subject (characteristics of the awarding process: awarding in a triumphal situation, wide coverage in the media, etc.), as a rule, provides for the provision of certain material goods, benefits to its owners. The combination of moral and material incentives in awards increases its effectiveness, defines priority areas of development, and requires the joint use of incentive aspects (spiritual and material).

Based on the fact that state awards are enshrined in legislation as the highest form of official incentives, it is necessary to study their characteristics, goals, and functions from the perspective of the legal incentive system of the object of study.

At the same time, an analysis of the legislation on state awards shows the presence of factors that negatively affect the functioning of the awards institution. On the one hand, there are cases of legal regulation of state awards, and on the other hand, this issue has not been fully and comprehensively studied from a theoretical standpoint.

State awards are state incentives for socially useful activities. Incentive refers to the public recognition of a person's socially useful activity through awards for their achievements. Individual achievements can be realized in various fields and at different levels. The circle of persons who have achieved such success is also established by law.[5]

Analyzing the concept of "reward," it is assumed that a person is rewarded in the form of gratitude for doing useful work. Awarding is carried out through direct rewarding. Every person, in the course of carrying out their labor activity, profession or specific research, can create discoveries, innovations that are beneficial to the masses, or as a result of sincerely carrying out their labor activity, profession or specific research, achieve results that are socially beneficial to the masses. Those who are recognized as the most acceptable will be awarded state awards. Each incentive shall have the following aspects:

1) the beneficiary is financially and morally encouraged; his achievements are publicly recognized and positively evaluated; have a legal character; are carried out by authorized entities in the established order;

2) for the legal or public services of the beneficiary.

Generalizing the above, the state award can be defined as follows: the state award is the highest form of awarding citizens for great merits in economics, science, culture, art, protection of the Motherland, state building, education, healthcare, protection of human rights, charitable activities and other services to the state.

Foreign citizens and stateless persons who have rendered services for the Republic of Uzbekistan may also be awarded state awards of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In addition, one person shall be awarded, as a rule, one order, medal or certificate of honor. Honorary titles are also not awarded repeatedly.

According to Article 6 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 22, 1996 "On State Awards" (with amendments and additions to this Law by the laws adopted on August 28, 1996, August 29, 1999, August 29, 2000, August 29, 2003, December 3, 2004), the presentation for awarding state awards shall be submitted by the Chairman of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Chairman of the Senate of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Chairman of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis, the Chairman of the Constitutional Court, the Supreme Economic Court, the The presentation of foreign citizens to the award is carried out in agreement with the Ministry of Foreign Affairs.

The presentation of citizens to the next award is carried out three years after the previous incentive. In exceptional cases, citizens may be presented without taking into account the time spent on prior incentives. Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on awarding state awards shall be published in the mass media.

Article 2 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Awards" states that the title of "Uzbekistan Hero," "Orders, medals, honorary titles and the Certificate of Honor of the Republic of Uzbekistan are considered state awards."

The title of "Uzbekistan Hero" and the medal "Golden Star" were established as a high-level award in the Republic of Uzbekistan. According to the Statute of the Law of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 5, 1994 "On the establishment of the title of "Uzbekistan Hero" and the establishment of the Supreme Decoration - the medal "Oltin Yulduz," the title of "Uzbekistan Hero" is a high-level award and is awarded to citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan for their heroic service to the state and the people.

Article 11 of the law lists the orders of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which are: the Order of "Mustakillik," the Order of "Amir Temur," the Order of "Jaloliddin Manguberdi," the Order "Buyuk xizmatlari uchun," the Order of "El-Yurt Hurmati," the Order "Fidokorona xizmatlari uchun," the Order of "Mehnat Shuhrati," the Order of "Soglom Avlod uchun" of I and II degree, the Order of "Shon-sharaf" of I and II degree, the Order of "

According to the Statute of the Law of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Establishment of the Order of Independence" dated May 5, 1994, the Order of Independence is awarded to citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan for their significant contribution to the establishment and strengthening of an independent state of law, ensuring peace and development in the republic.

According to the Statute of the Law of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 26, 1996 "On the Establishment of the Order "Amir Temur," by this order, citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan are awarded for outstanding merits in strengthening statehood, outstanding contributions to the development of architecture, science, literature and art, including military skills.

According to the Statute of the Law of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 30, 2000 "On the Establishment of the Order "Jaloliddin Manguberdi," this order is awarded to military personnel who have demonstrated high military skills, heroism and courage in protecting the borders of the Motherland, the soil of our motherland, the independence of our country and preserving it as a puppy's eye.

According to the Statute of the Law of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 29, 1996 "On the Establishment of the Order "Buyuk Xizmatlari Uchun," citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan and citizens of foreign states are awarded with this order for significant services in the development of science and technology, economy and culture,

significant contribution to the development of interstate cooperation and the implementation of domestic and foreign policy of Uzbekistan.

According to the Statute of the Law of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 28, 1998 "On the Establishment of the Order "El-Yurt Hurmati," this order is awarded to citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan who have made a significant contribution to strengthening the independence of the country, its economic power, raising national spirituality, culture, who are worthy of their work, scientific, public work and diligence, and patriotism.

According to the Statute of the Law of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 29, 2003 "On the establishment of the Order "Fidokorona xizmatlari uchun," this order is awarded to individuals who have made a significant contribution to the economic and cultural development of the country, strengthening the country's defense capability and ensuring national security, peace and stability in society, strengthening interethnic solidarity, ensuring the well-being of the people, recognizing their contribution to the development of the country with their knowledge and experience, serving as exemplars of selflessness

According to the Statute of the Law of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Establishment of the Order "Mehnat Shuhrati" dated August 30, 1995, this order is awarded to citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan for their great work contributing to the development of the economy and culture, the improvement of the well-being of the people, the preservation of peace and stability in Uzbekistan.

According to the Statute of the Law of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Establishment of the Order of Honor" dated August 30, 1995, citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan are awarded with this order for selflessness and courage in defending the Motherland, for great merits in strengthening the defense power and national security in Uzbekistan, increasing the combat readiness of the armed forces and ensuring law and order.

According to the Statute of the Law of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 5, 1994 "On the Establishment of the Order of "Dustlik," by this Order, citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan are awarded with great achievements in the work of strengthening friendship, mutual understanding and harmony among representatives of all nationalities and nationalities living in Uzbekistan, for the development of friendship and multilateral cooperation of the people of Uzbekistan with the peoples of other countries.

It is known that in the life of society, the importance of healthcare workers for the preservation of people's health and their healthy lifestyle is unparalleled. It is precisely for this reason that in our country, valuing the services of medical workers, encouraging them to work on themselves, continuously improving their professional qualifications, and encouraging the acquisition of medical knowledge are an integral part of the state's stimulating legal policy. The Law of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 4, 1993 "On the Establishment of the Order "For a Healthy Generation," the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 6, 1999 "On the Support of the International Ibn Sina Foundation," the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 1, 2005 "On Improving the Labor Payment System for Medical Workers" make a significant contribution to the introduction and promotion of high-quality services in the field of medicine.

On March 4, 1993, the President of Uzbekistan issued a decree on the establishment of the Order "For a Healthy Generation." The main purpose of such a high award is to protect

motherhood and childhood, strengthen the health of the younger generation, educate them spiritually, morally and physically, and encourage people who have made a worthy contribution to the work of instilling in them a sense of patriotism and love for their homeland - Uzbekistan. - Б. 94].

On the basis of the above proposal, the XII session of the Supreme Council of Uzbekistan, held on May 7, 1993, adopted a Law on the establishment of the Order "For a Healthy Generation." According to the Law "On the Establishment of the Order "For a Healthy Generation," the order is considered two-level (I and II degrees). Level I is considered a higher level. For high merits, they are awarded with this order for a period of 3 years. As a rule, they are first awarded with the Order of the II degree and then the Order of the I degree. (articles 2-4 of the law).

According to the Statute of the Law of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Establishment of the Order of Honor" dated August 30, 1995, citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan are awarded with this order for selflessness and courage in defending the Motherland, for great merits in strengthening the defense power and national security in Uzbekistan, increasing the combat readiness of the armed forces and ensuring law and order.

According to the Statute of the Law of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 5, 1994 "On the Establishment of the Order of "Dustlik," by this order, citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan are awarded with great achievements in the work of strengthening friendship, mutual understanding and harmony between representatives of all nationalities and nationalities living in Uzbekistan, for the development of friendship and multilateral cooperation of the people of Uzbekistan with the peoples of other countries.

Article 12 of the law establishes a rule on medals, which are: "Oltin Yulduz" medal, "Jasorat" medal, "Sodiq xizmatlari uchun," "Shuhrat" medal.

The medal "Jasorat" may be awarded to citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan or non-citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan for their courage in maintaining public order, saving people's lives, state and public property during natural disasters, fires and other emergency situations.

According to the Statute of the Law of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 5, 1994 "On the Establishment of the "Shuhrat" Medal, this medal is awarded to citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan and citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan who have achieved great achievements through their honest work in the development of the economy, science and culture of the republic, the upbringing of the younger generation in the spirit of patriotism and loyalty to the ideas of national independence and social development.

According to the Statute of the Law of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 6, 2007 "On the Establishment of the Medal "For Loyal Services," this medal is awarded to citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan who have demonstrated high professional skills, devotion to military and patriotic duty. for great merits in strengthening the defense capability and national security of the country, increasing the combat effectiveness of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan and ensuring human rights in Uzbekistan. In some cases, persons who are not citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan may also be awarded the Medal "For Loyal Services."

Honorary titles are of particular importance in the award system. Honorary titles are a recognition of the high merits of people of certain professions in society and are part of spiritual and moral incentives.

There are honorary titles such as People's Artist and People's Protector, and today many of our compatriots are awarded these awards. However, there is no difference between an artist and a singer, and there are no legal norms regulating their status. Therefore, state awards, as the main and important form of incentives, constitute the core of state incentive policy. The improvement of the state awards system allows for the full implementation of stimulating policies.

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